

Golden Term, Golden Series

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1 Introduction

1.1 What is the Golden Term?

The golden term exhibits special properties through equivalent transformations, commutative laws, and the use of the binomial formula. Unlike the golden ratio, infinitely many natural numbers $x > 1$ can be substituted into the term. The Golden Term has the following form. $x \in \mathbb{N}, x > 1$ and $g \in \mathbb{R}$

$$g := \frac{1 + \sqrt{x}}{2} = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{\sqrt{x}}{2} \quad (1)$$

In combination with a rational coefficient, term transformation and equivalent transformation allow for special results. The coefficient is as follows. $x \in \mathbb{N}, x > 1$ and $r \in \mathbb{Q}$

$$r := \frac{x - 1}{4} \quad (2)$$

1.2 What is the Golden Series?

The Golden Series converges and has the Golden Term as its limit, summands are the inverse of the golden term and the named coefficients as follows.

$$r \cdot \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{g^n} = g \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{x - 1}{4} \cdot \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\left(\frac{1 + \sqrt{x}}{2}\right)^n} = \frac{1 + \sqrt{x}}{2} \quad (4)$$

2 Characteristics of the Golden Term

2.1 Square of the golden term

The square of the golden term is equal to the term itself added to the coefficient of the series.

$$g^2 = g + r \quad (5)$$

$$\left(\frac{1 + \sqrt{x}}{2}\right)^2 = \frac{1 + \sqrt{x}}{2} + \frac{x - 1}{4} \quad (6)$$

Proof using the first binomial formula and equivalent transformations

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{1 + \sqrt{x}}{2}\right)^2 &= \frac{1 + 2\sqrt{x} + x}{4} \\ &= \frac{2 + 2\sqrt{x} + x - 1}{4} = \frac{2(1 + \sqrt{x}) + (x - 1)}{4} \\ &= \frac{1 + \sqrt{x}}{2} + \frac{x - 1}{4} \end{aligned}$$

2.2 Quotient of the golden term

The quotient of the coefficient and the golden term is equal to the reciprocal of the golden term.

$$\frac{r}{g} = \frac{1}{g} \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{\frac{x-1}{4}}{\frac{1+\sqrt{x}}{2}} = \frac{-1 + \sqrt{x}}{2} \quad (8)$$

The equation will be proven below using equivalent transformations, commutative law, and the third binomial formula.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\frac{x-1}{4}}{\frac{1+\sqrt{x}}{2}} &= \frac{x - 1}{4} \cdot \frac{2}{1 + \sqrt{x}} \\ &= \frac{(\sqrt{x} - 1)(\sqrt{x} + 1)}{4} \cdot \frac{2}{\sqrt{x} + 1} = \frac{-1 + \sqrt{x}}{2} \end{aligned}$$

2.3 golden term subtracted by one

The quotient of the coefficient and the golden term is equal to the golden term itself subtracted by one.

$$\frac{r}{g} = g - 1 \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{\frac{x-1}{4}}{\frac{1+\sqrt{x}}{2}} = \frac{1+\sqrt{x}}{2} - 1 \quad (10)$$

$$\frac{1+\sqrt{x}}{2} - 1 = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{\sqrt{x}}{2} - \frac{2}{2} = \frac{1+\sqrt{x}-2}{2} = \frac{-1+\sqrt{x}}{2}$$

2.4 Special case: golden ratio

Substituting $x = 5$ yields $r = 1$ in the golden term, revealing the properties of the golden ratio.

$$g^2 = g + r \Leftrightarrow g^2 = g + 1 \quad (11)$$

$$\left(\frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2}\right)^2 = \frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2} + \frac{5-1}{4}$$

$$\frac{r}{g} = g - 1 \Leftrightarrow \frac{1}{g} = g - 1 \quad (12)$$

$$\frac{\frac{5-1}{4}}{\frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2}} = \frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2} - \frac{5-1}{4}$$

Setting $x = 5$ in the golden series yields the following for $r = 1$ and the limit of the golden ratio.

$$r \cdot \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{g^n} = g \quad (13)$$

$$\frac{5-1}{4} \cdot \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\left(\frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2}\right)^n} = \frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2} \quad (14)$$

In summary, it can be said that the properties of the golden term can be transferred to the golden ratio.

3 Convergence of the golden series

$$\frac{x-1}{4} \cdot \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\left(\frac{1+\sqrt{x}}{2}\right)^n} = \frac{x-1}{4} \cdot \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{2}{1+\sqrt{x}}\right)^n \quad (15)$$

Application of the ratio criterion to proof convergence

$$a_{n+1} = \left(\frac{2}{1+\sqrt{x}}\right)^{n+1}, a_n = \left(\frac{2}{1+\sqrt{x}}\right)^n \quad (16)$$

$$\frac{a_{n+1}}{a_n} = \frac{\left(\frac{2}{1+\sqrt{x}}\right)^{n+1}}{\left(\frac{2}{1+\sqrt{x}}\right)^n} = \frac{2}{1+\sqrt{x}} \quad (17)$$

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{a_{n+1}}{a_n} = \frac{2}{1+\sqrt{x}} < 1 \quad (18)$$

for $x > 1 \Rightarrow$ convergent, for $x < 1 \Rightarrow$ divergent, for $x = 1 \Rightarrow$ no statement.
Multiplication by the coefficient of the series yields the reciprocal of the golden term.

$$r \cdot \frac{1}{g} = \frac{1}{g} \quad (19)$$

$$\frac{x-1}{4} \cdot \frac{2}{1+\sqrt{x}} = \frac{(\sqrt{x}-1)(\sqrt{x}+1)}{4} \cdot \frac{2}{\sqrt{x}+1} = \frac{-1+\sqrt{x}}{2} \quad (20)$$

This showed that the golden series converges for $x > 1$

4 Limit of the golden series determined by geometric series

$$\frac{x-1}{4} \cdot \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\left(\frac{1+\sqrt{x}}{2}\right)^n} = \frac{x-1}{4} \cdot \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{2}{1+\sqrt{x}}\right)^n \quad (21)$$

Application of the geometric series with $index = 0$

$$\frac{x-1}{4} \cdot \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\left(\frac{1+\sqrt{x}}{2}\right)^n} = \frac{x-1}{4} \cdot \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left(\frac{2}{1+\sqrt{x}}\right)^n - \left(\frac{2}{1+\sqrt{x}}\right)^0 \quad (22)$$

$$= \frac{x-1}{4} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{1 - \frac{2}{1+\sqrt{x}}} - 1\right) = \frac{x-1}{4} \cdot \frac{2}{-1 + \sqrt{x}} \quad (23)$$

Applying the third binomial formula to the coefficient r

$$\frac{(\sqrt{x}-1)(\sqrt{x}+1)}{4} \cdot \frac{2}{\sqrt{x}-1} = \frac{1+\sqrt{x}}{2} \quad (24)$$

The limit of the golden series is the golden term.

$$\frac{x-1}{4} \cdot \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\left(\frac{1+\sqrt{x}}{2}\right)^n} = \frac{1+\sqrt{x}}{2} \quad (25)$$

5 Exponentiation of the golden term

Different powers of the limit can be determined by shifting the index of the golden series.

$$\frac{x-1}{4} \cdot \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\left(\frac{1+\sqrt{x}}{2}\right)^n} = \left(\frac{1+\sqrt{x}}{2}\right)^1 \quad (26)$$

$$\frac{x-1}{4} \cdot \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\left(\frac{1+\sqrt{x}}{2}\right)^n} = \left(\frac{1+\sqrt{x}}{2}\right)^2 \quad (27)$$

$$\frac{x-1}{4} \cdot \sum_{n=-1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\left(\frac{1+\sqrt{x}}{2}\right)^n} = \left(\frac{1+\sqrt{x}}{2}\right)^3 \quad (28)$$

$$\frac{x-1}{4} \cdot \sum_{n=-2}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\left(\frac{1+\sqrt{x}}{2}\right)^n} = \left(\frac{1+\sqrt{x}}{2}\right)^4 \quad (29)$$

$$\frac{x-1}{4} \cdot \sum_{n=-3}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\left(\frac{1+\sqrt{x}}{2}\right)^n} = \left(\frac{1+\sqrt{x}}{2}\right)^5 \quad (30)$$

The geometric series is used to verify equation (27).

$$\frac{x-1}{4} \cdot \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\left(\frac{1+\sqrt{x}}{2}\right)^n} = \frac{x-1}{4} \cdot \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left(\frac{2}{1+\sqrt{x}}\right)^n \quad (31)$$

$$= \frac{x-1}{4} \left(\frac{1}{1 - \frac{2}{1+\sqrt{x}}} \right) = \frac{x-1}{4} \left(\frac{1+\sqrt{x}}{-1+\sqrt{x}} \right) \quad (32)$$

$$= \frac{(\sqrt{x}-1)(\sqrt{x}+1)(\sqrt{x}+1)}{4(\sqrt{x}-1)} = \left(\frac{\sqrt{x}+1}{2}\right)^2 \quad (33)$$